

Skills 4 eosc

D3.1 Policy makers and civil servants training plan

Lead Partner:	GRNET
Version:	2.0
Status:	Submitted draft not yet approved by the EC
Dissemination Level:	PU - Public
Document Link:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10728514
DOI:	10.5281/zenodo.10728514

Deliverable Abstract

Deliverable D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan, is a document that describes the general overview of the plan of the training activities related to policymakers and civil servants during the project. The information included is describing all the training activities, the dependences with other tasks and WPs in the project, the training calendar and the learning platform which will be used for the training purposes / needs.

This document will be updated with deliverable D3.2 "Evidence-based policy and Public Administration training final report" which is the final report for the training activities in T3.1 and will be delivered at the end of the project.

Skills4EOOSC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058527 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10040140]

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

This work by Parties of the Skills4EOSC Project is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The Skills4EOSC project is co-funded by the European Union Horizon Europe programme under grant n° 101058527 and by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee under grant n° 10040140.

DELIVERY SLIP

	<i>Date</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Partner/Activity</i>	<i>Date</i>
<i>From:</i>		Nana Anastasopoulou, Betty Evangelinou	GRNET	13/01/2023
<i>Moderated by:</i>		Betty Evangelinou	GRNET	
<i>Reviewed by:</i>		Elena Giglia	UNITO	22/06/2023
<i>Approved by:</i>		Emma Lazzeri, Sara di Giorgio	GARR	30/06/2023
<i>Updated by:</i>		Betty Evangelinou	GRNET	29/02/2024

DOCUMENT LOG

<i>Issue</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Comment</i>	<i>Author</i>
v0.1	13.01.23	<i>Creation of initial ToC</i>	<i>Nana Anastasopoulou (GRNET)</i>
v0.2	15.02.23	<i>Updated ToC and input</i>	<i>Betty Evangelinou (GRNET),</i>
v0.3	30.03.23	<i>Contributions added</i>	<i>Betty Evangelinou (GRNET), Katrine Weisteen Bjerde (HK-Dir), Lars Bjonnes (HK-Dir)</i>
v0.4	20.04.23	<i>Contributions added</i>	<i>Betty Evangelinou (GRNET), Sonja Filiposka (UKIM)</i>
v0.5	30.05.23	<i>Contributions added</i>	<i>Betty Evangelinou (GRNET), Dominique Green (DCC), Emma Lazzeri (GARR), Marina Sanchez Moreno (UC3M), Katrine Weisteen Bjerde (HK-Dir), Sonja Filiposka (UKIM)</i>
v0.6	16.06.23	<i>Draft version ready for review</i>	<i>Betty Evangelinou (GRNET)</i>
v0.7	22.06.23	<i>Final Review</i>	<i>Elena Giglia (UNITO)</i>

v1.0	30.06.23	<i>Final Version ready for submission</i>	<i>Betty Evangelinou (GRNET), Ognjen Prnjat (GRNET), Emma Lazzeri (GARR), Sara Di Giorgio (GARR)</i>
V2.0	29.02.24	<i>Updated version as per Periodic Review Comments</i>	<i>Betty Evangelinou (GRNET), Emma Lazzeri (GARR), Sara Di Giorgio (GARR)</i>

TERMINOLOGY

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
CC	Competence Centre
WP	Work Package
MVS	Minimum Viable Skill-set
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
OS	Open Science
RDM	Research Data Management
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ToT	Train of/the trainer
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues
Q&A	Questions and Answers
QA	Quality Assurance
RDA	Research Data Alliance
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
IG	Interest Group
BBB	Big Blue Button
JRC	Joint Research Centre

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	6
2	Training goals / objectives and activities	8
	2.1 Training Approach	8
	2.2 Target indicators.....	12
3	Training requirements analysis	13
	3.1 Target profiles and Minimum Viable Skill-set (MVS) approach	13
	3.2 Thematic Areas.....	14
	3.3 Key Messages, Learning Outcomes, and Training Curriculum.....	18
	3.4 Instructional methods - Types of courses.....	19
	3.5 Competence Centres and Master Trainers	22
	3.6 Communities/Groups to be targeted	22
4	Learning platform and training material preparation	25
	4.1 Skills4EOSC learning platform	25
	4.2 Training Material Preparation	29
	4.3 Training evaluation, quality assurance and certification framework ..	35
	4.4 Collaboration with other projects / organizations	37
5	Training Curriculum	40
6	Training events management	48
7	Conclusions	59

Table of Figures and Tables

Figure 1: T3.1 Training Activities Timeline.....	9
Figure 2: “What themes do you believe would be the most important for training?”	17
Figure 3: “Which group(s) of policymakers are you focusing on?”	23
Figure 4: Skills4EOOSC Learning Platform (Homepage)	25
Figure 5: Access to the Skills4EOOSC platform	27
Figure 6: FAIR-by-design methodology schema	30
Figure 7: Indicative timeline of the planned pilot training events	57
Table 1: List with Train-the-trainers for methodology	32
Table 2: Initial Key Messages.....	40
Table 3: Initial Key Considerations.....	40
Table 4: WP3 Full Curriculum.....	41
Table 5: Current Plan for the ToTs courses	48
Table 6: Indicative timetable for 1st ToT.....	49
Table 7: Indicative timetable for 2nd ToT.....	51
Table 8: Indicative timetable for 3rd ToT.....	52
Table 9: Indicative timetable for 4th ToT.....	54
Table 10: Initial Plan for the community trainings	55

1 Introduction

This deliverable defines the initial plan that is being established for the training activities for policymakers and civil servants, as part of T3.1 “Open Science training for policymakers and civil servants” of the Skills4EOsc project.

The main idea behind the training in Skills4EOsc and more specifically in T3.1 is to provide training material and deliver training to governmental groups like civil servants and policymakers as well as agencies. This will be done through a three-step training procedure, that will be followed during the project lifetime:

1) First of all, the training material that will be used in trainings needs to be developed. The work that has been done for the Landscaping and skills mapping to professional profiles in T2.1 will give insights for the specific skills needed per Target group category. Based on the results of the landscaping survey, a Minimum Viable Skill-set approach is followed for each of the profiles of policymakers and civil servants, with the material covering essential skills.

Moreover, in order to give guidelines on the principles that need to be followed for the development of the material that will be used for the trainings, the consortium, in T2.3, is drafting a FAIR-by-design methodology. In order to adapt this methodology through the entire project, WP2 will deliver training courses on material development and best practices for the instructors/training material developers to be able to create the relevant material, not only in T3.1, but in the entire project, based on FAIR principles. Additionally, already available training material from other projects and resources is being collected in order to be evaluated for potential reuse and adaptation according to the needs of the professional profiles that have been identified and analysed.

2) When the training material development procedure is complete, the next two steps include training events, divided in two types:

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

2a) On the one hand, the Train-the-Trainer events for trainers in Competence Centres will be organized, in order to up-skill them on topics related to Open Science for evidence-based policy and public administration, for each participating country. These trainers will act as Master Trainers, that will use the training they received, to pass the knowledge to the relevant stakeholders in their communities.

2b) On the other hand, the second type of training events, that will come as a result of the Train-the-Trainer ones, will focus on capacity building and community training events per country, that will be provided by the Master Trainers based on the experience and skills acquired during the train-the-trainer events.

For the purposes of the training in Skills4EOOSC, a learning platform is also being developed, as part of WP7, that will help in gathering all the training material for the entire project in a single location, and provided to the trainers, based on the training needs of each community/target group. Anyone interested in a particular topic and level should be able to easily find and reuse the available resources. This platform will act as a one stop shop for all the professionals and communities to be trained. The courses included will be presented as live courses or lectures, online self-paced courses, or hands-on courses, in order to provide flexibility to the trainers.

3) Finally, in order to be able to evaluate the quality and success of the training events, a monitoring and feedback process will be established in T2.4, based on feedback material (surveys, feedback forms, etc.) that will be also provided to the trainers through the platform.

2 Training goals / objectives and activities

2.1 Training Approach

The main goal of the training activities in T3.1 is to enable the civil servants and policymakers and agencies to understand key concepts of OS, RDM and evidence-informed policy and acquire the necessary skills to adopt them in their everyday work.

To achieve this goal three initial activities have been envisioned within the project:

- analyse the needs and requirements and develop relevant **training material** tailored to the needs of these specific professional profiles of the civil servants and policymakers and agencies,
- organize **Train-the-Trainer** project-wide training events, in order to up-skill the Master Trainers in the Competence Centres, and provide them with all the necessary tools and material,
- support trainers to pass on this knowledge to the target communities in each country, through **national community training** events that will be used as pilots to the overall training procedure in Skills4EOSC.

In order to achieve the above, a training activities timeline (see fig. 1) has been established, that describes in detail the training plan that will be followed in T3.1, depicting, in parallel, all the dependences between the different activities and WPs within the project.

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

Figure 1: T3.1 Training Activities Timeline

Based on the timeline in Fig. 1 we have identified concrete periods for the different activities that will be performed in T3.1, taking into account the dependences on the activities of the other WPs. In this figure/diagram, these periods are labelled with the relevant activity title, while the analysis of the different activities is provided in the next chapter.

Training material Preparation (M7-M18): As mentioned before, in order to identify the material that will be developed for the trainings of the specific professional profiles targeted in the project, WP2 has developed a landscaping and mapping of the skills needed per profile. Therefore, the training material preparation starts with policymakers, after the first release of the Minimum Viable Skill-set (MVS)¹ for the relevant profile in M6. Then, in M9, the MVS for Civil Servants is also added on the table, with a final deliverable D2.1 that includes all the professional profiles targeted in the project, to be added to the training material preparation. An important aspect in the training material design and preparation is the FAIR-by-design methodology that needs to be adopted. Using the methods described in the initial workshop on the FAIR-by-design methodology on M8 and followed the final guidelines provided at the end of the first year of the project (M12), with

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/7686263>

an additional workshop on M14, the training material preparation will end by M18, achieving the milestone “M3.1 Science4Policy Training Material available”, to pass the baton to the Train-the-trainers events. Finally, parallel to the training material preparation, Train-the-trainers sessions will also be provided by WP2 to the consortium members participating as instructors in the material development. These sessions will cover training on methodologies, tools and practices that need to be used for the material development.

Identification and Engagement of the Master Trainers (in CCs) for ToTs and the Relevant Communities for pilot trainings (M7-M18/M28):

In parallel and additionally to the training material development, the MVS will give insights and guidelines on the selection of the people and communities that need to be engaged for the trainings. Having in mind the professional profiles that will be targeted, specific training strategy meetings will be organised with participants from all the countries involved in the project, as well as representatives from the relevant communities of the policymakers and civil servants. In collaboration with WP7, the Master Trainers and the Competence Centres for the Train-the-Trainers events will be identified (before M18), as well as the targeted Communities for the pilot policy trainings. During this period and before M28, each participating country will be requested to identify at least one (1) or probably more national relevant Community to be trained in a pilot training. It is worth mentioning that the engagement period of the relevant stakeholders does not actually have an end date, as during the training events, additional trainers and communities might be also included in the trainee groups, either as Master Trainers, or as additional communities for pilot training.

Train-the-Trainers events (M19-M28): Having completed with the training material preparation, within a period of ten (10) months, the Train-the-Trainers events will start taking place, aiming to provide the necessary competences to specific people that will act as Master trainers in the Competence Centres in their country, relevant to policy making and public administration. These events will be performed by trainers selected by the

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

consortium, using the material developed during the Training Material Preparation phase.

Community Trainings (M29-M33): Finally, when the Train-the-Trainers events have been completed, the pilot training events of the relevant communities will follow. These events will take place within a period of five (5) months, where at least one (1) pilot training event will be performed in each participating country in the project.

Training Feedback and Evaluation (M23-M36): During this period, and after the first Train-the-trainers event that will take place within the first four (4) months of the Train-the-Trainers event phase, a Feedback and Evaluation period will start on M23 and last until the end of the project in M36, where participants in the trainings will provide feedback on the training material, as well as on the actual training events that will take place. Within this period, T3.1 will make use of the Quality Assurance procedures that will be established in the project (T2.4), in order to re-evaluate the content and the effectiveness and efficiency of the training, and make the necessary adjustments for the upcoming trainings. At the end of the project, the final training material, additional resources from the trainings, as well as the final evaluation of the training activities will be provided in D3.2 “Evidence-based policy and Public Administration training final report”.

In parallel to all the above activities, the **learning platform** that will host all the trainings and training resources of the project will be developed by WP7. Using the platform, the Master Trainers and the targeted stakeholders will be able to have access to all the training materials and additional resources that will help them during the training processes. The same material can be also used as reference material afterwards. This learning platform will, therefore, serve as a single repository for all project-related training material, but also provide additional training opportunities via online self-paced courses that will further boost knowledge transfer and skills development.

For all the above, the main action points that have been identified, are the following:

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

- prepare a training plan including an indicative timeline for all training events that will be organized;
- keep an up-to-date calendar of training events;
- define internal project policies and templates that will support the training event organizers and the trainers, in collaboration with WP2;
- use the Skills4EOSC learning platform that will act as a repository for all the training materials and resources;
- prepare relevant WP-specific training materials, based on FAIR principles;
- establish collaboration with other relevant initiatives for the development of training material and insights.

2.2 Target indicators

The effectiveness of the defined project activities related to training will be measured using a number of target indicators, identified in the proposal stage.

The minimum number of training events that will be organized during the project lifetime is fifteen (15). In particular, the training plan based on the proposal and presented in the following sections includes:

- at least fifteen (15) training events for policy (we foresee at least one (1) Community pilot Training event per country);
- at least three (3) Train-the-Trainer (ToT) events for Competence Centres in WP3;
- at least one hundred fifty (150) people trained in total in WP3.

3 Training requirements analysis

3.1 Target profiles and Minimum Viable Skill-set (MVS) approach

A Skills4EOOSC Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) describes essential skills and competencies required to deliver OS outcomes for communities and organisations.

The development of the MVS profiles were based on a multi-tiered approach, including a landscape review, a public survey, and collaborative working groups. Initially, a landscape review was conducted within the first six months of the project. The starting point for the review was the framework of the ten roles identified by the EOOSC Working Group on Skills and Training report in 2021². The Skills4EOOSC Task 2.1 focused on a subset of the framework roles outlined in the working group report and included:

- data stewards and other data professionals, more broadly,
- researchers,
- knowledge brokers who act as ‘honest brokers’ in the science-society interface,
- research infrastructure professionals.

Secondly, a public survey was conducted as a means to provide feedback on the MVS approach and targeted roles as defined in a milestone report. Based on this public survey, the list of roles for data professionals were expanded. These roles include those that are instrumental in shaping Open Science, including policymakers and civil servants.

Additionally, a list of sources used in writing the MVS profiles was collaboratively compiled by the T2.1 partners, working in subgroups

² European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (2021) Manola, N., Lazzeri, E., Barker, M. et al., Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science – Report from the EOOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group, Manola, N.(editor), Lazzeri, E.(editor), Barker, M.(editor), Kuchma, I.(editor), Gaillard, V.(editor), Stoy, L.(editor), Publications Office, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>

dedicated to each role. The sources collected include reports, peer-reviewed journal articles, deliverables from other EC funded projects, and government policy documents.

Each MVS profile includes an introduction for the rationale for treating the role as an Open Science actor. Additionally to the essential skills and competences of each profile, the introduction also includes suggestions for a range of organisational contexts. The organisational context varies by role and includes research performing organisations (RPOs), which are particularly relevant for the profiles targeting researchers, public administration, governmental sectors and organisations, national agencies, national funding organisations, and competence Centres. These organisational contexts show which environments in which these OS actors typically work or are affiliated with.

Finally, Skills4EOSC includes various work packages like WP3 that will use the MVS to inform their work on training and curriculum development. Therefore, a key component in the development in the profiles was gathering feedback from partners across these work packages in order to align the MVS content and design and content with their needs. The profiles developed in D2.1 is illustrative of this multi-tiered process.

3.2 Thematic Areas

After the first draft of the MVS for the policymakers and the definition of their professional profile, with the skills, competences and organisational context, a landscaping questionnaire was conducted in order to start identifying the Thematic Areas and Communities that should be included in the training. The questionnaire was distributed to the participating countries of T3.1 after the first draft of the MVS for the policymakers (M8), with the intention to get some first insights of their needs and aims for training in policy, in a national level.

The main thematic areas the respondents could choose from were selected by our work group as a result of discussions in several meetings, covering also areas identified during the proposal stage. We ended up with 5 different

main themes related to the profile, that were considered important to offer both to policymakers and later to civil servants, during the training events conducted in this task, which are described below:

Science 4 Policy: Training in science for policy equips policymakers and civil servants with essential skills to understand scientific concepts, methodologies, tools and the latest advancements across various disciplines. This enables them to make evidence-informed decisions and develop policies grounded in scientific expertise. Fostering collaboration between scientists and policymakers to integrate scientific knowledge into policy recommendations helps to address emerging societal challenges, by providing a robust evidence base for policy development and implementation.

Principles of Open Science: Open Science empowers policymakers and civil servants to embrace transparency, collaboration and innovation. Open access to scientific information, data or publications fosters the unrestricted access and exchange of knowledge for decision makers, enhancing transparency, accountability, integrity of the work done, as well as trust in the decision-making progress. Open science also maximizes the public impact of research by making findings accessible and usable for citizens, non-governmental organizations, and policymakers themselves, promoting democratic decision-making and facilitating the translation of research into societal benefits and more effective and inclusive policies.

FAIR Data Principles: FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) Data Principles enhance the ability of policymakers to optimise the value and impact of research data in decision making. Findable and accessible data enables policymakers to understand the need for a broader range of evidence, while interoperability is important for the facilitation of data integration and sharing, which in collaboration with other stakeholders, will help them draw insights from research studies and address complex societal challenges. Furthermore, re-usability of data promotes efficiency and cost-effectiveness, by reducing duplication of efforts and maximising the utility of collected data. By training in the fundamentals of FAIR data principles,

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

policymakers and civil servants can harness the full potential of research data, enabling data-driven decision making and advanced scientific progress for the prosperity of society.

Managerial and ELSI aspects: Effective Research Data Management is essential for policymakers to navigate the complexities of data-driven decision-making. By receiving training in RDM, policymakers and civil servants can acquire the necessary basic knowledge in order to be able, if necessary, to organise, store and safeguard their data throughout its life-cycle. Moreover, understanding ELSI aspects is vital for them to address the ethical, legal, and social implications of scientific and technological advancements, ensuring they are implemented responsibly, respecting human rights, privacy and societal values. ELSI training also helps to anticipate and mitigate potential risks and harms associated with emerging technologies. By integrating ELSI aspects into policy development and implementation, policymakers can strike a balance between scientific progress and societal well-being, fostering responsible and sustainable innovation for the benefit of all.

Use of Open Science for evidence-based policy: Open-science in evidence-based policy can equip policymakers with all the necessary knowledge and skills to leverage open science practices for informed decision making. Strategies and guidelines, as well as practical examples and case studies can showcase how open science has been successfully utilised in evidence-based policy making across various domains. Engagement with relevant stakeholders and the public through collaborative processes is also crucial to explore citizen science initiatives and interdisciplinary collaborations. Such training allows policymakers to exploit the possibilities of open science and improve the quality, transparency and effectiveness of evidence-based policy making.

Based on the above, the distribution of the countries' answers to the question *"What themes do you believe would be the most important for training"*, is provided below:

Figure 2: “What themes do you believe would be the most important for training?”

From figure 2, it is prominent that Principles of OS and FAIR Data Principles were the most relevant themes according to the country representatives. These principles seem to be the basis of most trainings in the field and are themes that other trainings are also built upon. It is also a good indication on the importance of these two themes, when 14/15 respondents focus mainly on them. Moreover, Managerial and ELSI aspects are also considered important with 9/15 answers, with Science4Policy and OS for evidence-based policy with less participation.

These first results help to understand the bigger picture regarding the themes that should be included in the training. In developing the actual training material, it will be crucial to have a more thorough analysis on the needs of the specific target groups in mind. Thus, training material for policymakers and civil servants on a specific topic (e.g. Principles of open science), will not be another generic training on the field, but will be adapted to their needs and quite different from the training material that could be used to train researchers on the same topic.

3.3 Key Messages, Learning Outcomes, and Training Curriculum

As mentioned before, within this task, the training material that will be developed, will be based on the skills and competences that will be identified for each corresponding profile. Moreover, after the consultation with the relevant stakeholders and the landscaping questionnaire, the main themes that policymakers and civil servants have found of interest to be trained on, have also been identified. Taking into account both the results of the community understanding (through the questionnaire, but also through consultation meetings with representatives of each country), the MVS approach followed in WP2 for the two profiles, as well as the FAIR-by-design methodology detailed in paragraph 4.2, the following approach regarding the content of the training material has been determined:

- 1) The first step in developing the training material is to identify the **key messages** that need to be conveyed to policymakers and civil servants. Key messages should be concise, impactful statements that capture the essence of the subject matter and ensure that the core content is effectively communicated. They should highlight the most important concepts, principles and frameworks relevant to their roles that the trainees need to understand and apply to their work. Moreover, they may be based on emerging policy challenges, organizational goals, gaps in knowledge and skills of the participants, or challenges in their day-to-day work. By conducting a thorough analysis of key messages, training developers will be effectively structure the content and prioritize the information that should be included in the training material.
- 2) Another step in the training material development process is the definition of the **learning outcomes**, i.e. the desired results of the training program. The learning outcomes specify the knowledge, skills and attitudes the participants should acquire upon completion of the training. When defining learning outcomes, it is crucial to align them with the needs and expectations of policymakers and civil servants. Their roles, responsibilities, and the challenges they face must be considered, to determine the competencies that will best

empower them to fulfil their duties effectively. This relevance helps participants see the practical value of the training and encourages them to apply the newly acquired knowledge and skills in their professional contexts.

3) To enhance the effectiveness of the above, it is also important to conduct in parallel, a **needs assessment**, in order to gain insights on the specific knowledge gaps and training requirements of the civil servants and policymakers. This needs assessment is planned to be performed during the community meetings that will be held in parallel to the training material preparation, where representatives from the targeted profiles will be invited for feedback (section 4.2.5). This step will help training instructors to understand the existing knowledge base, skill levels and areas of improvement in the field, in order to tailor the material to address their unique needs and enhance their capabilities.

4) Once the key messages, learning outcomes and needs assessment results are established, the next step is to start designing the **training curriculum**. The curriculum will be divided in modules that cover different aspects of the subject matter, with relevant content covering the key messages, some case studies, guidelines and practical examples that illustrate their application in real-world contexts. The different instructional methods that are considered to be used to deliver the training, also form the training curriculum, and are described in the next section. Having an engaging training curriculum will enhance the motivation and interest of the trainees and encourage them to participate actively in the learning process, rather than passively receiving information.

3.4 Instructional methods - Types of courses

Designing a training curriculum is a process that requires not only the definition of the content that will be delivered, but also the identification of the instructional methods that will be selected, in order to ensure effective engagement and learning experiences for the trainees. Thus, the format of the courses varies depending on the nature of the training and the means that are used for its implementation. Of course, the content of the course and its learning outcomes also affect the type of the course or training event.

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

In Skills4EOSC and more specifically in T3.1 we foresee different formats in the training courses and events that will take place during its entire lifetime, selected each time based on the targeted trainees and the content that will be delivered within the course.

For the training of the policymakers and civil servants, as already described, we foresee two types of training events to take place. The first one will be the Train-the-Trainers events for the Master Trainers in the Competence Centres, that will be performed mainly online. According to the content of each course and the level of interaction by the trainee, the type of the event will be decided. As the training content is still early in the development, we have conducted an initial assessment for the types of events to be delivered:

Interactive Webinars: These are live webinars, where trainees can join real-time, interact with the presenters and participate in discussions or Q&A sessions. Webinars allow for immediate feedback, clarification of concepts, and addressing specific concerns or questions. Their main focus is to deliver information in a wider audience and provide a broad understanding of the subject topic.

Hands-on trainings/Workshops: Similarly to the Interactive Webinars, the Workshops are also conducted in real-time, but they are more interactive and participatory. These types of trainings have a different structure from the webinars, and may include, additionally, quizzes and assignments, discussions, demonstrations, group activities, live access to online infrastructures, interactive online tools, etc. Workshops also allow for immediate feedback and clarifications, but they focus more on active and experiential learning, collaboration, engagement and skill-building. They are often conducted in smaller groups of participants.

Self-paced Online Courses: Self-paced online courses offer learners the flexibility to study at their own pace and convenience, explore content in depth, and personalize their learning experience. Their structure is more modular, and typically include a mix of multimedia resources such as text-based lessons, videos, interactive quizzes, case studies, and supplemental

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

materials. This variety of content formats caters to different learning styles, making the course more engaging and accessible.

The second type of training events includes the Community pilot trainings that will be conducted in each country. In these trainings, the trainers will use the material from the Train-the-Trainers events and provide training to their selected communities of civil servants and policymakers and agencies. These events might be conducted either online or in-person and will differ in time, as these kinds of professionals rarely have much time available for training. It is worth mentioning, that to increase the engagement, tailored training should be delivered, as well as local language is highly recommended and will be considered for the pilot training events.

Based on the profiles of the trainees and the purpose and outcome of each training, the following types can also be included in the previous list:

Lectures: In-person lectures allow trainers to deliver information, theories, and concepts directly to participants. These sessions can be accompanied by slide presentations, visual aids, or demonstrations to enhance understanding.

Policy Round-tables: Policy-focused round-table discussions where policymakers can explore specific policy issues, share their experiences, and collectively develop recommendations or guidelines for implementation.

Panel Discussions: Panel discussions with a diverse group of experts and practitioners in open science and policy-making. These discussions can focus on specific themes, challenges, or emerging trends in the field. Participants can engage in Q&A sessions and benefit from the collective knowledge and experiences of the panelists.

Case Study Presentations: Present real-life case studies related to open science and policy-making. Participants can analyse the cases, identify challenges, and propose solutions or strategies.

Interactive Demonstrations: Demonstrate tools, platforms, or technologies in real-time, allowing participants to observe and interact with the tools

directly. Interactive demonstrations provide a practical understanding of how certain practices can be implemented and their potential impact.

The selection and variety of the instructional methods within a training curriculum influences significantly the participation and engagement of the trainees, having essential impact on the results of each training.

3.5 Competence Centres and Master Trainers

The initial step in order to be able to organise the Train-the-Trainer project-wide training events, is to identify the Competence Centres and the Master Trainers for each country participating in the project. Based on the specific target groups of policymakers and civil servants, addressed in T3.1, all organisations participating in the task are requested to identify the relevant people/stakeholders in their countries that will be trained in the Train-the-Trainers events.

For this purpose, a consultation within the participating organisations has been organised, in order for each organisation to identify the most relevant Master Trainers per country, in the fields of policy making and public administration. For each country, at least one (1) Master Trainer will be assigned to participate in the Train-the-trainers events.

Collaboration with WP7 will have a real impact towards this direction, through the identification of the Competence Centres (CCs), the landscaping of existing CCs and organisations relevant to the professional profiles targeted in the project, but also the set-up of new CCs and the user support network that is planned in that WP.

3.6 Communities/Groups to be targeted

Communities identification for pilot trainings

When the Train-the-Trainers events are finished and the Master Trainers have acquired the necessary knowledge and skills, they will provide at least one (1) pilot training to their countries, to pass this knowledge to the relevant communities/stakeholders. There is a large amount of relevant actors the

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

trainers could choose from, so in order to map out which groups were targeted by the trainers, we used the landscaping questionnaire³. The purpose was to map the status of plans and target groups for such events and to identify any challenges that need to be addressed in order for the events to be successful.

The results of the 15 countries that participated in the questionnaire to the question *“Which group(s) of policymakers are you focusing on?”* are shown in the Figure 3 below:

Figure 3: “Which group(s) of policymakers are you focusing on?”

The respondents were allowed to select multiple options for this question, based on the organisational context identified in MVS of the profiles. We see that Top level of Research performing organisations and Funding organisations were the target groups that most respondents intend to focus their effort on. Governmental organisations and Ministries followed with less participation, but also additional ideas were thrown into the table, such as Open Science professionals related to policy making and Schools for Public Administration.

In the question *“What challenges do you see in planning or performing the training?”* we received different answers with the most common to be the concern of finding interested and relevant audience, but also the need to

³ The questionnaire was an internal tool that was used to initiate the discussion with the related partners in the project, there are no public results.

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

provide an actually useful training, tailored to the needs of each target group, and not another generic training on Open Science. Another challenge was the size, the format and the depth of the training as well as the time that these communities could dedicate for such trainings.

The landscaping questionnaire was an initial attempt to encourage and support the participants to understand the aim of the task but also start identifying possible stakeholder communities for the pilot trainings in their countries. In addition to that, training strategy meetings with the task participants are also performed, including discussions, guidelines and exchange of ideas between the different countries, and will continue to be performed regularly until the final definition of the pilot training events. Within these meetings, the representatives responsible for coordinating the training events for the two roles Policymakers and Civil Servants in their countries, will also have the opportunity to discuss any ambiguities or challenges in planning the training events (which communities to invite, how to reach out, coordination within each partner country, etc), in order to organise the pilot trainings with success.

Discussions with and feedback from representatives of the different partners and targeted communities

Additionally to the above, these meetings will serve as a communication medium with representatives from the targeted communities that will be invited to discuss the needs of the different groups and give insights on how to best design the training events for their community.

Such assessment will help the instructors during the training material preparation to structure the content and the format of the courses based on the real needs of the trainees, in order to achieve the highest impact possible. Moreover, feedback from the actual users of the training on the developed material will also be explored, as an early evaluation process.

4 Learning platform and training material preparation

4.1 Skills4EOSC learning platform

In order to provide and deliver training courses and share related materials, the Skills4EOSC project has developed a dedicated learning platform. The Skills4EOSC learning platform is based on the Moodle Learning Management System, an open source software released under the GNU General Public License. The [Moodle learning platform](#)⁴ was selected as it is designed to provide trainers, administrators and learners with a robust, secure and integrated system to create personalised learning environments. The Skills4EOSC learning platform is available at <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/>.

Figure 4: Skills4EOSC Learning Platform (Homepage)

⁴ https://docs.moodle.org/402/en/About_Moodle

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

The platform will mainly serve as a repository for the official project training events, where trainers and trainees will be able to have access to all the relevant content and resources of the training events related to the separate WPs of the project. Using the Moodle capabilities, the instructors/content creators of the training material and the trainers will provide different types of courses such as live courses or recorded lectures, online self-paced courses, or hands-on courses, depending on the training that they will perform in each occasion. Resources and courses on supplementary tools that will be used for the training material preparation, will also be provided through the learning platform.

Moreover, the platform will be used by the consortium members, as a tool for hosting web-conferences and projects meetings such as Plenaries, General Assembly, Technical Board, Virtual Round Tables, Work Packages and Tasks. Web conferencing and meetings will be hosted using the Big Blue Button plug-in for Moodle, which redirects to BlueMeet⁵, a video conferencing service developed by GARR. Within the platform, a reserved area has been included for the project partners to access the pages dedicated to the documents and meetings of the different work packages and tasks. To allow access to this area, a specific role (Partner) has been created in the platform with specific permissions.

Access to the platform is provided via both [Moodle's email-based self-registration plugin](#)⁶ and [eduGain's](#)⁷ federated authentication service (see Figure 5).

⁵ <https://blue.meet.garr.it/b>

⁶ https://docs.moodle.org/402/en/Email-based_self-registration

⁷ <https://edugain.org/>

Figure 5: Access to the Skills4EOSC platform

To position itself in the European landscape of emerging common standards for training and learning resource platforms and catalogues, Skills4EOSC uses a metadata standard defined by [RDA \(Research Data Alliance\) Education And Training On Handling Of Research Data IG](#)⁸. Metadata enable course search within the platform, as well as browsing the results using filters and faceted navigation. The [set of metadata](#)⁹ identifies key characteristics of learning resources that are important both for content creators to include with the resources they create, and for learners searching for learning resources to find the ones they are looking for more easily and to identify whether those resources meet their needs.

A fruitful collaboration with [Ni4OS Europe training platform](#)¹⁰ technical team ensured the Skills4EOSC platform is built on experience and lessons learned by a previous project in terms of metadata management and discovery.

⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/education-and-training-handling-research-data.html>

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/record/6769695#.ZHh9IXZBxmN>

¹⁰ <https://training.ni4os.eu/>

User support

In order to provide support to users accessing the Skills4EOSC learning platform, a dedicated email account (learning-support@lists.skills4eosc.eu) has been created on the platform's home page, which redirects emails to the support service set up by the project. All user requests in relation to the management of courses and content on the platform will therefore be handled by the support service.

Architectural Notes

The Skills4EOSC learning platform is based on Moodle 4.1, the latest Long Term Support release, which ensures product life-cycle management over an extended period of time, including updates to address technical issues and security patches.

The Skills4EOSC Moodle deployment relies on the [Bitnami Helm Chart](#)¹¹. Federated authentication is provided using the standard Moodle OpenID Connect plugin. OpenID Connect mediates the eduGAIN SAML federation through the GARR Satosa proxy.

Moodle and BlueMeet, the GARR video conferencing service based on BigBlueButton, interact via the standard Moodle BBB plugin. Both plugins are free and open source. The BlueMeet enabling tool, BigBlueButton, was deployed using the [Ansible repository](#)¹².

GDPR compliance

The Skills4EOSC project is bound by European Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR). Skills4EOSC uses the Moodle learning platform as part of its training services for relevant stakeholder training activities. Moodle is an open source project that is GDPR compliant. The Moodle instance used by Skills4EOSC is

¹¹ <https://github.com/bitnami/charts/tree/main/bitnami/moodle/>

¹² <https://github.com/unistra/bigbluebutton/>

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

maintained and managed by GARR. The instance and all third party plug-ins are hosted on GARR's own web servers in Italy (EU). Therefore, GARR is responsible for the protection of users' personal data when using the Skills4EOSC learning platform. All registered users of the Skills4EOSC learning platform must accept the [Privacy Policy](#)¹³, which specifies the purposes and legal basis for using personal data.

4.2 Training Material Preparation

4.2.1 FAIR-by-design methodology

In order to start preparing the Training Material throughout the project, the FAIR-by-design approach studied and delivered in WP2 will be followed. The methodology for FAIR-by-design learning materials is described in D2.3 which will be available in its final form in M12, after completing the public consultation and project internal quality assurance procedure. The FAIR-by-design methodology aims to empower the popular backward instructional design process with additional activities related to the creation of FAIR learning materials from both, the perspective of trainers aiming for future reuse, and the trainees requiring easy access and usability. Within the D2.3 document a detailed step-by-step workflow (see Fig. 6) is proposed guiding the training material designers through all the phases of the material preparation process, while ensuring the final result will adhere to the FAIR principles.

¹³ <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/admin/tool/policy/viewall.php?returnurl=https%3A%2F%2Flearning.skills4eosc.eu%2F%3Fredirect%3D0>

FAIR-by-design Methodology

Figure 6: FAIR-by-design methodology schema

The main goal of following the FAIR-by-design methodology is not to start from scratch with the creation of the training materials needed in WP3, but aim to reuse the existing training materials in the EOSC community as much as possible, while adhering to the IPR implications. Following the methodology will ensure that the training materials for the trainers will be well structured, described using a common metadata schema, and properly licensed for reuse outside the project, while adhering to a collective quality assurance process. The methodology also incorporates guidance on the creation of not only the learning content, but also the accompanying materials that aim to facilitate their use by trainers including information on the training organisation, assessment and feedback gathering.

This approach will ensure that the initial training materials developed for the ToT events will include all necessary information needed to successfully organise the national pilot training events. Additionally, the FAIR-by-design methodology process can also be followed when adapting and localising the ToT learning materials for the purposes of developing the learning content per country.

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

To ensure that the WP3 team can practically put into action the step-by-step FAIR-by-design workflow, specialised project level training will be conducted by WP2 trainers following the official publication of D2.3. During the development phase of these training materials, the WP2 team will be in close collaboration with WP3 aiming to fully understand the requirements and focus on facilitating the training materials design by using relevant examples and developing reusable templates.

FAIR-by-design methodology training

As mentioned in paragraph 2.1, during the Training Material Preparation period, the FAIR-by-design methodology training will take place (M14), that will give the consortium members the necessary guidelines and tools for the preparation of the training material based on FAIR principles.

The complete training will consist of a series of sessions that will focus on the different steps of the FAIR-by-design methodology. Each session will provide guidelines on how to practically implement the respective step of the methodology, incorporating interactive examples and exercises that showcase the development of FAIR learning materials on the topic of Open Science. In this way the trainees will be able to actively learn the methodology and test its application in their development process. Part of the training will also be focused on introducing template documents that aim to facilitate the material generation such as course content map, material hierarchy organisation, and structured document layout with content placeholders and examples for attribution and licensing. The training content will be aligned with the platforms developed for use within the project such as learning environment, repositories, shared workplace, and similar collaboration tools enabling trainees to combine them all together.

4.2.2 Train-the-trainers tools and methodologies for the consortium members

In addition to the FAIR-by design methodology training, and during the Training Material Preparation period, train-the-trainers events will also take place. These will focus on tools and methodologies for the instructors within

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

the consortium that are working on the development of training materials. These training events will provide instructions and hands-on exercises on processes and tools that could or need to be used for the training material preparation and the training execution. Some of the ToT sessions may be designed as self-paced learning sessions, whereas a single ToT session may include more than one topics. The ToTs for methodology will be delivered between June 2023 and December 2023. The first ToT related to EUSurvey was delivered on June 7, 2023.

Indicatively, a list of already identified ToT courses for the instructors is provided in the Table 1 below.

Table 1: List with Train-the-trainers for methodology

Topic	Description
Tools for interaction	This session will present common tools for interaction in remote training sessions. Specific tools like Mentimeter as well as built in functionalities such as BBB tool will be introduced together with possible usage scenarios within training sessions.
EU Survey	The EU Survey tool will be the objective of a demo session that will also show how the tool can be used to support Skills4EOSC activities such as co-creation and feedback collection after training events.
Feedback collection	This session will focus on effective methods and strategies for collecting feedback during training sessions. Participants will learn about different feedback collection techniques and how to utilize feedback to improve the training experience. The Skills4EOSC template for feedback form will be presented in collaboration with task 2.6.
Slide Design	In this session, participants will gain insights into the principles of effective slide design. They will learn about visual hierarchy, use of images and colors, and how to create visually appealing and engaging slides that enhance the learning experience.
Speech	This session will delve into the art of delivering impactful speeches during training sessions. Participants will learn techniques for effective verbal communication, including voice modulation, body language, and engaging

	storytelling, to captivate and inspire their audience.
Learning Platform	The Skills4EOSC learning platform, described in paragraph “4.1 Skills4EOSC learning platform”, based on Moodle and BBB, will be the central focus of this session. Participants will be introduced to the platform and its features, exploring how it supports effective online training and collaboration. They will learn how to navigate the Moodle interface, access course materials, participate in discussions, and submit assignments. Additionally, participants will discover the functionalities of BBB (BigBlueButton), an integrated web conferencing tool within the platform, which enables live interactions, virtual classrooms, and real-time collaboration. Through hands-on exercises and demonstrations, participants will gain practical knowledge on using the Skills4EOSC learning platform to create engaging and interactive learning experiences for their trainees.
Training of Trainers Guide	“How to teach Open Science?” This session will provide trainers with a comprehensive guide on teaching Open Science concepts. Participants will learn about the key principles, methodologies, and resources necessary to effectively train others on Open Science practices. The training will be based on existing material as the ORION OS.
Training techniques	This session will explore different training techniques commonly used in learning environments. Participants will examine the pros and cons of various techniques, such as Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), hands-on exercises, and assessments, and understand how to select and utilize the most appropriate techniques based on learning objectives and audience needs.
Zotero	This session will introduce participants to Zotero, a powerful reference management tool. Participants will learn how to use Zotero to organize and cite references, create bibliographies, collaborate with others, and efficiently manage their research and learning materials. The session will show how Zotero library is used to support Skills4EOSC activities.
Ethics and RRI	This session will delve into the ethical considerations and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles within the context of training. Participants will explore the

	importance of ethical conduct in research and learn how to integrate RRI practices into their training programs.
Wrap up session	In this final session, participants will summarize and reflect upon the key concepts and skills learned throughout the training program. They will have the opportunity to ask questions and engage in an interactive discussion with all the trainers, clarifying any doubts and solidifying their understanding before concluding the training.

The above courses cover a wide range of tools and methodologies that are typically used in training material development, but also in training organisation and delivery, and were proposed by the consortium. This is an indicative list; as the project progresses with the development of the actual material, some tools or methodologies might be also added in this courses list, as we identify additional needs for the training development.

4.2.3 Existing training material - additional early training events

Based on the FAIR-by-design methodology, the aim in the material development process is to identify existing training materials and resources in the EOSC community and reuse them as much as possible, instead of creating everything from the beginning. Therefore, as part of T2.5 in WP2, a landscaping report was created, giving an overview of existing Train-the-Trainer material. This is not a formal deliverable for Skills4EOSC, but an internal deliverable meant for other tasks and work packages in the project, like T3.1, to use in their work on creating Train-the-Trainer courses. The overview of the resources from the landscaping process is found in a written report and an Excel sheet with short descriptions of and links to the different resources (web sites, documents, on-line courses etc).

Some of the collected Train-the-Trainer resources are generic while others are directed specifically to training trainers on a particular topic within Open Science or even within a specific discipline. Thus for the policymakers and civil servants in T3.1, the aim is to identify the material that seems most

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

relevant and adapt it to the specific needs and competences of these two professional profiles.

Although the main aim for the T2.5 landscaping was to collect resources on Train-the-Trainer events, these resources are often intertwined with material on end-user training, thus the landscaping report also links to a significant number of such resources. As WP3 will also deliver pilot end-user/community training events, these will also be of relevance. It must also be acknowledged, that during the training preparation phase, additional resources related to policymakers and civil servants will also come to light and examined, in order to support the instructors into delivering essential and tailored material for training.

To this end, training events that will take place within this period will also be explored. These will include events that are already planned to be performed by the partners of the consortium, that could be of relevance to the project and the scope of WP3, but also relevant events that will be delivered by organisations outside the consortium. This list of events will be available for the instructors to be informed, participate or gain access to relevant resources, and will act as a live document that will be constantly updated by new events as time progresses. These events will be also used as early training events, to provide insights on the end-user needs and expectations, but also serve trainers to acquire expertise in training specific audiences.

4.3 Training evaluation, quality assurance and certification framework

After each training event of the project and during the entire period from the first training until the end of the project, it is foreseen to perform regular evaluations through feedback from the participants in each training. This feedback will be used to identify potential gaps in training, or possible recommendations for future trainings. Based on this feedback, changes on the training material will be also considered. The methods and strategies that will help the trainers to collect this feedback during each training session

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

will be provided by the ToT session for Feedback Collection, that will be delivered for the consortium members (paragraph 4.2.2) and will be available in the learning platform.

However, in order to anticipate essential modifications in the training material and the training structure, T2.4 encompasses the creation of a quality assurance (QA) and certification framework for the learning materials, aligning with endorsed criteria and governance mechanisms. The objective is to develop a comprehensive approach that covers the entire lifecycle of learning resources, from identifying learning needs and outcomes to delivering and evaluating materials. The framework also ensures the adaptability of training materials to changes in technology and policy.

The methodology employed for this task begins with an independent analysis of two key drafts delivered inside the project: the Catalogue of Open Science Career Profiles - Minimum Viable Skillsets (developed by T2.1) and the FAIR-by-design methodology (developed by T2.3). Essential criteria from these drafts will be extracted to construct a checklist that will serve as the basis for assessing these aspects. This checklist will then inform the design of qualitative and/or quantitative indicators for evaluation.

Following this, a merging process will take place, combining the two QA frameworks based on the Minimum Viable Skillsets and the FAIR-by-design methodology. This integration will identify areas of overlap and potential gaps, ensuring internal consistency and replicability within the project. The framework will also address Ethical, Legal, and Social Issues (ELSI) related to Open Science (OS) career profiles, skillsets, and materials. Collaborating with T2.2, specific indicators will be incorporated to consider relevant OS regulations, policies, and legislative interventions that impact the development of OS skills, QA, and certification mechanisms.

In designing these indicators, the approach will focus on providing recommendations and advice rather than imposing strict guidelines. The aim is to measure progress and implementation, emphasizing continuous improvement on each criterion.

The final stages of implementation involve conducting workshops to introduce the framework and gather feedback from the community. These workshops will provide an in-depth explanation of the methodology and practical examples, enabling trainees to learn and apply the framework in their own development processes. The feedback received will be instrumental in refining and enhancing the framework. Additionally, a draft of the framework will be published, and an interactive visual representation is planned to be made available on the project's website. Trainees will be equipped with the necessary skills to navigate and interpret the framework effectively, facilitating widespread dissemination and comprehension. This interactive approach will also provide an opportunity for the community to review and contribute to further improvements of the framework.

4.4 Collaboration with other projects / organizations

During its action, Skills4EOOSC will seek collaborations and create synergies with relevant projects, organisations and initiatives.

European Joint Research Centre

Skills4EOOSC WP3 was built on solid collaboration with the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC)¹⁴ and its Community of Practice (CoP) of trainers for Science for Policy, some of whom are working as participants in the Skills4EOOSC project. Thanks to this collaboration, a series of activities and exchanges are undergoing, with particular attention to tasks 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4 and 8.5. The JRC CoP already collaborated to design and deliver an online training session delivered for WP3 participants on January 18th 2023. The material from the JRC Science4Policy course that includes essential material for researchers who would like their research results to have greater policy impact, but may not have the know-how to communicate effectively with policymakers, will be used and integrated in the training materials that will be designed in WP3.

¹⁴ https://commission.europa.eu/about-european-commission/departments-and-executive-agencies/joint-research-centre_en

HE EOSC Projects and EOSC Partnership

Skills4EOSC is committed to deliver results in support of the EOSC Partnership.

Under the Vademecum that was drafted by the EOSC-A¹⁵, Skills4EOSC is collaborating with several projects in the EOSC context. Skills4EOSC is part of various groups in the EOSC-Forum platform, and the project members are active in the EOSC-A Task Forces as well as in the EOSC-A organisation, including its Board of Directors.

Links are active also with the other tripartite actors, the European Commission and the EOSC Steering Board (SB). The project has already established links with the EOSC SB, especially around the recent Opinion Paper on EOSC Data Literacy¹⁶ that includes recommendations on establishing Data Competence Centres in Europe.

Thanks to the frequent HE EOSC-related project Coordination meetings organised by the EC, Skills4EOSC has established close collaboration with the EC with the aim of aligning project activities with expectations at European level.

WP3 benefits from this collaborative environment as it allows Skills4EOSC to effectively manage the co-creation activities with various stakeholder types and impact on the policy aspects related to the EOSC.

National Initiatives for Open Science and EOSC

Skills4EOSC project Consortium includes partners involved in national initiatives for Open Science and EOSC (ICDI¹⁷, NFDI¹⁸, etc) and is building on these links to engage the national community. The project is also seeking the collaboration of National Initiatives and Projects outside its consortium, that

¹⁵ <https://www.eosc.eu/>

¹⁶ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Opinion paper on EOSC FAIR data literacy, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/716842>

¹⁷ <https://www.icdi.it/it/>

¹⁸ <https://www.nfdi.de/>

are creating Competence Centres in Countries that are not covered by Skills4EOSC. The Project will offer to selected initiatives the opportunity to participate to the ToT sessions and events, including the ones organised by WP3. In the context of the national tripartite events, the Skills4EOSC project was presented and, in some cases, project participants effectively managed to exploit the preliminary outputs of WP3 to deliver important key messages to policymakers (Rectors, RPO Presidents, Ministries, etc) that were designed in task 3.1 and 8.5.

Other relevant Projects and Initiatives

Besides the ones already mentioned, and as part of T8.2, the project is also setting up collaborations with other relevant Projects (RiTrain Plus¹⁹, Ni4OS Europe²⁰, PATTERN²¹, etc) and initiatives (ENRIO²²). The aim is to avoid duplication of efforts and build on existing expertise to effectively reach the project objectives.

Members of the Skills4EOSC Consortium are active in a number of different initiatives related to the Science for Policy interface acting on Open Science, such as CoARA²³, RDA²⁴, OECD²⁵, UNESCO²⁶, and TOPS²⁷. These important links will be exploited to facilitate the uptake of project results in the community.

¹⁹ <https://ritrainplus.eu/>

²⁰ <https://ni4os.eu/>

²¹ <https://www.pattern-openresearch.eu/>

²² <http://www.enrio.eu/>

²³ <https://coara.eu/>

²⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

²⁵ <https://www.oecd.org/>

²⁶ <https://www.unesco.org/en>

²⁷ <https://science.nasa.gov/open-science/transform-to-open-science>

5 Training Curriculum

As mentioned in par. 3.3 and the described methodology, first we identified some initial Key Messages and Key Considerations for Policy Makers and Civil Servants.

Table 2: Initial Key Messages

No.	Key Message
01	Open science is essential for advancing research and innovation
02	Open science is the new normal
03	Open science is a multi-stakeholder endeavour
04	Open science leads to more transparency, reproducibility, reliability and accountability
05	There are challenges to implementing open science, but there are ways to overcome them
06	Policy plays a critical role in supporting open science
07	What can Policy Makers do for OS to succeed
08	Policy Makers need to invest in new competencies in Open Science and related professional profiles and careers
09	There are costs associated to not supporting open science and FAIR management of research outputs
10	Policy makers / civil servants can make use of OS outputs for evidence-based decisions
11	There are many successful examples on real-life scientific topics with high societal impact of use OS in policy making.
12	Public organizations should develop strategies for implementing open science policies
13	Scientists' engagement is key to effective and equitable evidence-informed decision-making
14	Ethical, Legal and Societal issues are central to support Open Science and can be found in most of the messages above. As an example, a well-tailored, balanced, Intellectual Property legal framework is a key factor to foster innovation, access and re-use, and incentivize creators
15	Open Science-positive policies can become the catalyst for change in reward and hiring practices, as well as responsible research assessment

Table 3: Initial Key Considerations

No.	Considerations
01	Am I collecting and documenting data systematically with accompanying metadata for future reference?
02	Have I considered privacy concerns while handling sensitive data and adhered to legal and ethical standards?
03	How can I facilitate collaboration by sharing non-sensitive data and advocating for open data platforms?
04	Am I staying updated on evolving open science practices and adopting new technologies for data management?
05	How can I foster collaborative relationships with other government agencies to promote open science?
06	How can I communicate data to the public in accessible ways for evidence-based policy

	making?
07	Am I staying informed about best practices and training opportunities related to open science and data management?
08	How can I advocate for open science practices and inspire colleagues to embrace transparency?
09	How can I uphold ethical principles throughout data collection, sharing and use in my daily work?
10	How Open Science and Data Management can be used in different fields of public administration?

These initial Key Messages and Key Considerations were elaborated and reshaped into numerous modules, based on specific Learning Objectives and Outcomes that should be included in the training. Therefore, the full curriculum of the training, as defined at the moment of writing this deliverable, includes **20 main modules** and they are analysed below:

Table 4: WP3 Full Curriculum

No.	Module (related KM)	Sub-Module	Topics
01	Open Science is the New Norm - Fundamentals of Open Science (KM2)	Open Science, FAIR and RDM Principles	Introduction to Open Science - Open Science is the new norm
			Open Science principles and how they relate to FAIR data and research data management.
			Open Access, Open Data, Open Source, Open Methodology, Open Peer Review
02	Open Science is Essential for Advancing Research and Innovation (KM1)	Benefits of OS for scientific progress	Explore the connections between open science, innovation and collaboration
			Explore and discuss the tangible benefits of open science for scientific progress and society at large.
		Open Science in Practice: Case Studies	Open Science in Practice: Realizing Scientific Advancements
03	Accountability and Transparency in Open Science (KM2-4)	Core Principles of Accountability and Transparency	Core principles of accountability and transparency in open science
		Open Science and trust-building	Connection between open science, trust-building, and its implications for industry and the general public.
			Case studies where open science practices have positively influenced public and industry trust in research
		Research Integrity	Present the vital link between open science and research integrity

			Examples of Research Misconduct: How Research Integrity relates and could have prevented issues
		Best Practices and Methods for Transparency and Accountability	Integrity by design: methods and workflows for a transparent research project
04	Legal and Ethical Frameworks and Considerations in Open Science (KM14)	Overview of the EU Legal Framework on Copyright, (Personal) Data Protection and the Data and Digital Legislation	Introduction to the EU Regulatory Framework on Copyright, Personal Data and Data and Digital Legislation, focusing on selected relevant legislative acts to Open Science.
		Issues concerning Ethics in Research and Open Science	Introduction to the main issues concerning Ethics in Research and Open Science
05	Challenges and Opportunities for Open Science in the EU Regulatory Framework (KM14)	Challenges and Opportunities for Open Science in the EU Regulatory Framework: Copyright and the Data and Digital Legislation	Identifying and discussing some of the main provisions and mechanisms available in the (i) EU Copyright Law and (ii) Data and Digital Legislation that may impact access, sharing and (re) use of data.
		Challenges and Opportunities for Open Science in the EU Regulatory Framework: (Personal) Data Protection and Ethics	Risk based approach to data sharing, decision making on data sharing, data accuracy, confidentiality/privacy, ethics of data curation.
06	Data Governance and Legislative Strategies for FAIR Research (KM9)	Planning the FAIRification of data	Documentation; Data life cycle; Access to Data; Data Licenses; Efforts; Semantic Models.
		Identifying practical "how to" tools to go FAIR	Documentation; Data life cycle; Access to Data; Data Licenses; Efforts; Semantic Models. Open Data and Fair Data; Open data portals; Data Management Plan; Privacy Policy; Fair-by-design vs FAIRification; Legislative strategies for making high-value datasets FAIR;
07	Open Science and Society (KM6 - KM11)	Societal Implications and Policy Interface of Open Science	Societal Implications and economic impact of Open Science: Citizen Science from Galileo to post-truth populism
		Real life examples showing the high societal and economic impact of	Analysis of real-world examples where open science has led to societal advancements.

		OS	
		Success stories	Success stories and experiences in realizing societal and economic benefits through open science policies
08	Open Science vs. Closed Science (KM9)	Closed science	What is closed science - Present case studies that highlight the consequences of research misconduct, data opacity, and closed science practices
		Challenges and Ethical Dilemmas	challenges and concerns related to research misconduct and data opacity and ethical dilemmas related to closed science practices.
		Economic impact of closed science and associated costs	Explore the economic impacts of open science and FAIR data management compared to closed science
			Economic implications of Open Science and broader economic consequences
		Culture of Openness	Presentation of various scenarios involving resistance to open science initiatives within organizations
09	Investing in Open Science (KM8)	Need for investments	The role of funding in promoting open science practices
			Real-world case studies of organizations or countries that have invested in open science competencies
			Explore different funding models and mechanisms supporting Open Science.
		Funding in Local Context	Examination of how to apply such practices to the local context.
		Funding allocation	Securing and allocating funding to implement Open Science practices in projects
		Data Repositories	Establishing Efficient Data Repositories
10	Capacity Building and Training Programs in OS (KM8)	Open Science Training Programs	Understanding Capacity Building in OS
			Identifying Training Needs
		Existing Open Science Training Programs	Existing open science training programs
		Institutional Support and Best Practices for OS training programs	Institutional Support for Capacity Building: Challenges and Best Practices
		National Initiatives	National Initiatives and Best Practices

11	Understanding Open Science and Its Stakeholders (KM3)	Open Science Stakeholders	Overview of Open Science principles and stakeholder involvement
			Significance of multi-stakeholder collaboration in Open Science.
12	Open Science and Evidence-informed Decision Making	Policy, Evidence and Evidence-Informed Decision Making	What is policy, evidence and evidence-informed decision-making
			Evidence-based policy vs non-evidence-based policy comparison
		Stakeholders involved in Evidence-informed decision making	Role of Open Science in informing policy-making
			Idealized roles at the interface between science and politics (Pure scientist, Science Arbiter, Issue Advocate and Honest broker), and how their roles really are implemented in reality
13	Open Science and AI	Introduction to AI	History of AI
			How AI works - Algorithms and machine learning models
		AI and Open Science	Open Access infrastructures for AI
			Open Access Data & Computer codes
		AI in evidence-informed decision - making	AI with and for Open Science
			Applications of AI in evidence-informed decision (use cases)
14	Evidence-informed decision making - outputs and tools (KM10)	Open Science outputs, Open Access and Data Management	Limitations & risks of AI
			Ethics & legal implications of AI
		Data analysis and evidence-informed decision making	Types of Open Science outputs, including open access publications, open data, and open-source software and their significance
			Finding and reusing scientific and public data (examples for Public Administration)
Statistical Analyses and Visualisation Graphs	Data Management and storing		
	Data Analysis in open science		
			Predictive modelling in evidence-informed decision making
			Limitations & risks of automated tools & data
			Basics of statistical analysis, including descriptive statistics, inferential statistics, and significance

			testing. Explain how to interpret data visualization graphs and their significance in communicating findings and insights in evidence-based decision-making.
15	Collaboration Strategies for Stakeholders	Strategies and Tools for effective collaboration	Role of open science in fostering collaboration among researchers, practitioners, and the public
			How to achieve scientists' engagement - skills and collaboration initiatives
			Case studies of successful collaboration in Open Science
		Creating a collaborative culture and impact evaluation	Creating a Collaborative Culture: Discuss how organizations can foster a culture of collaboration.
			Methods for evaluating collaboration's impact.
		Uncertainty and Complexity in Decision Making	Principles of effective communication, including audience awareness and message clarity.
How to communicate scientific uncertainty and complexity while maintaining trust.			
Effective Communication and Presentation Guidelines	Guidelines and best practices for effective communication with policy makers & how to define the messages for policy makers		
	Data Visualization and Storytelling: Strategies for presenting data and research findings using visualizations and narratives		
16	Policy-making in Open Science	Introduction to Open Science Policies	Role of policies in Open Science and their significance
			National and Regional Strategies
		Successful OS policy case studies	Case studies of regions with successful Open Science policy implementation.
17	Open science policies support open science practices (KM5-6)	Open Science policies support Open Science Practices	Open science policies and their impact on open science practices: Real-world examples showcasing how open science policies have facilitated open science practices
			Examination of the role of stakeholders in OS policy formulation and implementation.
		Challenges of Implementing and	The challenge of integrating open science practices within existing

		barriers to adopting Open Science	research paradigms.
			How traditional metrics of academic success might not align with open science
			Socio-cultural Considerations
			Resource and Infrastructure Limitations
			Real-world challenges researchers and policy makers face in implementing Open Science
		Barriers to adopting Open Science	
		Cultural Changes required for Open Science Adoption	Cultural changes required for Open Science adoption and potential solutions /strategies
		Culture Assessment	Assessment of the culture within different research institutions
		Open Science infrastructure	Introduction to open science infrastructure, its importance, and its components
			Case studies of open science infrastructures
Benefits and Challenges of Open Science Infrastructures			
18	Role of Policymakers in Supporting OS Practices (KM5-7-15)	Profiles of Policy Makers supporting OS	Case studies and profiles of policymakers who have been influential in supporting open science
		Essential Elements for OS policy development & implementation	Essential Elements for OS policy development and implementation
			Policy development and implementation exercise
		Responsible Research Assessment	Responsible Research Assessment initiatives including DORA, Leiden Metrics, The Metric Tide, and CoARA
			CoARA and DORA in Practice
			Assess the readiness and awareness of responsible research assessment practices in an institution: policy maturity and implementation
19	Implementing OS policies - Action Planning and Roadmap Development	Common Open Science Workflows	Key components of Open Science workflows
			Structure and principles of effective Open Science workflows.
		Overcoming Workflow Challenges	Common challenges in implementing Open Science workflows
20	Monitoring and Evaluation of Open Science Policies	Monitoring progress and Impact	Designing Effective Performance Indicators for Open Science Policies
		KPIs analysis	How the different indicators are effective in monitoring progress.
		Policy Adaptation	Policy Adaptation in Open Science:

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

			Navigating Change and New Evidence - Strategies and Case studies
--	--	--	---

All the material for these modules will be included as a self-paced course in the learning platform, with additional relevant activities, such as evaluation quizzes, exercises, forums, etc, in order the trainee to be evaluated for their skills acquisition but also to allow them to have access to additional information, through discussions and relevant material. Moreover, material that will be developed in the other tasks of WP3 will also be included in the learning platform as additional material.

Initial Feedback workshops and Needs Assessment discussions already provided insights on the described material, but more workshops and pilot activities are foreseen for the next period, in order to re-evaluate the content and finalise the structure of the Train of Trainers courses.

6 Training events management

For the trainings of T3.1, as already stated, we have two periods where training events will take place, within the project. The first period includes the Train-the-Trainers events that will start on M19 until M28 and then the second period includes the Community pilot trainings events, that starts on M29 until M33.

Even if it is too early to schedule the exact dates for the relevant events, an estimation with indicative dates within the two periods, when the different trainings will be performed, is already in place.

Train-the-trainers sessions – initial estimations

Based on the results of the landscaping questionnaire on the main themes for training, the initial plan for the Train-the-Trainers included a definition of these events based on the Thematic areas identified by the working group and selected by the countries representatives. Nevertheless, as we progressed with the training material development, the content of the Train-the-Trainers sessions was redefined, based on the Key Messages and Considerations identified and through thorough discussions and feedback activities. Additional relevant activities in the next period (e.g. planned pilot/testing ToT courses, feedback activities with trainers and end-users, etc.) will give us more insights on the final structure and content of the ToT courses, and will help us finalise the training material size, focus, structure and instructional methods that will be selected for each module.

Below you will find the current plan for the ToTs sessions.

Table 5: Current Plan for the ToTs courses

No.	Thematic Areas	Target Audience	Estimated (month)	Date
1	1 st short pilot/testing ToT (co-creation)	5-10 trainers	Q2 2024	
2	2 nd short pilot/testing ToT (co-creation)	5-10 trainers	Q2 2024	

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

No.	Thematic Areas	Target Audience	Estimated (month)	Date
1	1 st final ToT course: Open Science is the new norm	10-15 trainers	Q3 2024	
2	2 nd final ToT course: Open Science and Society	10-15 trainers	Q4 2024	
3	3 rd final ToT course: Open Science and Stakeholders	10-15 trainers	Q4 2024	
4	4 th final ToT course: Policy Making in Open Science	10-15 trainers	Q4 2024	

Based on the current plan, Table 5 includes the main Thematic Areas of each course, an indicative number of Master Trainers that will be trained in these courses, as well as an estimation of the period, during which they will be performed.

Besides the final ToT courses that are foreseen, we have identified the need to perform two (2) early pilot/testing ToT courses that will be used, in order to collect feedback from different participants on planned activities, size, duration and structure of the courses and thus co-create the final ones.

An indicative structure of the final ToT courses can be found below:

Table 6: Indicative timetable for 1st ToT

Time	Module	Duration	Activity	Duration per Activity	Sub-module
9:00AM	Welcome and Ice-breaking Activity	15 mins	Welcome and Course Introduction	10 mins	
			Ice-breaking Activity	5 mins	
9:15AM	01 - Open Science is the New Norm - Fundamentals of Open Science (KM2)	45 mins	Lecture	40 mins	Open Science, FAIR and RDM Principles
			Interactive Activity/Quiz	5 mins	Quiz
10:00AM	02 - Open Science is Essential for Advancing	45 mins	Lecture	15 mins	Benefits of OS for scientific progress
			Interactive Activity/Quiz	5 mins	Quiz

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

	Research and Innovation (KM1)		Lecture	20 mins	Open Science in Practice: Case Studies
			Interactive Activity/Quiz	5 mins	Quiz
10:45AM	Break	15 mins			
11:00AM	03 - Accountability and Transparency in Open Science (KM2-4)	50 mins	Lecture	10 mins	Core Principles of Accountability and Transparency
			Lecture	10 mins	Open Science and trust-building
			Lecture	10 mins	Research Integrity
			Interactive Activity/Discussion	15 mins	Best Practices and Methods for Transparency and Accountability
			Interactive Activity/Quiz	5 mins	Quiz
11:50AM	04 - Legal and Ethical Frameworks and Considerations in Open Science (KM14)	60 mins	Lecture	40 mins	Overview of the EU Regulatory Framework on Copyright, (Personal) Data Protection and the Data and Digital Legislation
			Lecture	20 mins	Issues concerning Ethics in research and Open Science
12:50AM	Lunch Break	60 mins			
1:50PM	05 - Challenges and Opportunities for Open Science in the EU Regulatory Framework (KM 14)	75 mins	Lecture	30 mins	Challenges and Opportunities for Open Science in the EU Regulatory Framework: Copyright and the Data and Digital Legislation
			Lecture	30 mins	Challenges and Opportunities for Open Science in the EU Regulatory Framework: (Personal) Data Protection and Ethics
			Interactive Activity/Discussion	15 mins	Q&A
3:05PM	Break	10 mins			
3:15PM	06 - Data Governance and Legislative	85 mins	Lecture/Interactive Activity - Discussion	40 mins	Planning the FAIRification of data

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

	Strategies for FAIR Research (KM9)		Lecture/Interactive Activity - Discussion	40 mins	Identifying practical "how to" tools to go FAIR
			Interactive Activity/Quiz	5 mins	Quiz
4:40PM	Closing Remarks and Course Summary	20 mins	Recap of Key Learnings	10 mins	
			Q&A Session	10 mins	
5:00PM	End of Course				

Table 7: Indicative timetable for 2nd ToT

Time	Module	Duration	Activity	Duration per Activity	Sub-module
9:00AM	Welcome and Ice-breaking Activity	15 mins	Welcome and Course Introduction	10 mins	
			Ice-breaking Activity	5 mins	
9:15AM	07 - Open Science and Society (KM6 - KM11)	80 mins	Lecture	20 mins	Societal Implications and Policy Interface of Open Science
			Lecture	35 mins	Real life examples showing the high societal and economic impact of OS
			Interactive Activity/Discussion OR Guest	20 mins	Success Stories
			Interactive Activity/Quiz	5 mins	Quiz
10:35AM	Break	15 mins			
10:50AM	08 - Open Science vs. Closed Science (KM9)	90 mins	Lecture	25 mins	Closed science
			Lecture	20 mins	Challenges and Ethical Dilemmas
			Lecture	20 mins	Economic impact of closed science and associated costs
			Lecture	20 mins	Culture of Openness
			Interactive Activity/Quiz	5 mins	Quiz
12:20PM	Lunch Break	60 mins			
1:20PM	09 - Investing	55 mins	Lecture	15 mins	Need for investments

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

	in Open Science (KM8)		Interactive Activity/Discussion	15 mins	Funding in Local Context
			Lecture	10 mins	Funding allocation
			Lecture	10 mins	Data Repositories
			Interactive Activity/Quiz	5 mins	Quiz
2:15PM	Break	10 mins			
2:25PM	10 - Capacity Building and Training Programs in OS (KM8)	45 mins	Lecture	10 mins	Open Science Training Programmes
			Interactive Activity/Discussion	10 mins	Existing Open Science Training Programs
			Lecture	10 mins	Institutional Support and Best Practices for OS training programs
			Interactive Activity/Discussion	15 mins	National Initiatives
3:10PM	Closing Remarks and Course Summary	20 mins	Recap of Key Learnings	10 mins	
			Q&A Session	10 mins	
3:30PM	End of Course				

Table 8: Indicative timetable for 3rd ToT

Time	Module	Duration	Activity	Duration per Activity	Sub-module
9:00AM	Welcome and Ice-breaking Activity	15 mins	Welcome and Course Introduction	10 mins	
			Ice-breaking Activity	5 mins	
9:15AM	11 - Understanding Open Science and Its Stakeholders (KM3)	15 mins	Lecture	15 mins	Open Science Stakeholders
9:30AM	15 - Collaboration Strategies for Stakeholders (KM13)	100 mins	Lecture	40 mins	Strategies and Tools for effective collaboration
			Lecture	35 mins	Creating a collaborative culture and impact evaluation
			Interactive Activity/Quiz	5 mins	Quiz

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

			Lecture	20 mins	Uncertainty and Complexity in Decision Making
11:10AM	Break	15 mins			
11:25AM	15 - Collaboration Strategies for Stakeholders (KM13) – cont.	65 mins	Lecture	60 mins	Effective Communication and Presentation Guidelines
			Interactive Activity/Quiz	5 mins	Quiz
12:30PM	12 - Open Science and Evidence-informed Decision Making	55 mins	Lecture	20 mins	Policy, Evidence and Evidence-Informed Decision Making
			Lecture	30 mins	Stakeholders involved in Evidence-informed decision making
			Interactive Activity/Quiz	5 mins	Quiz
1:25PM	Lunch Break	60 mins			
2:25PM	13 - Open Science and AI	55 mins	Lecture	15 mins	Introduction to AI
			Lecture	15 mins	AI and Open Science
			Lecture	20 mins	AI in evidence-informed decision - making
			Interactive Activity/Quiz	5 mins	Quiz
3:20AM	Break	10 mins			
3:30PM	14 - Evidence-informed decision making - outputs and tools (KM10)	55 mins	Lecture	10 mins	Open Science outputs, Open Access and Data Management
			Lecture	20 mins	Data analysis and evidence-informed decision making
			Lecture	20 mins	Statistical Analyses and Visualisation Graphs
			Interactive Activity/Quiz	5 mins	Quiz
4:25PM	Closing Remarks and Course Summary	20 mins	Recap of Key Learnings	10 mins	
			Q&A Session	10 mins	
4:45PM	End of Course				

Table 9: Indicative timetable for 4th ToT

Time	Module	Duration	Activity	Duration per Activity	Sub-module
9:00AM	Welcome and Ice-breaking Activity	15 mins	Welcome and Course Introduction	10 mins	
			Ice-breaking Activity	5 mins	
9:15AM	16 - Policy-making in Open Science	45 mins	Lecture	30 mins	Introduction to Open Science Policies
			Lecture/Interactive Activity - Discussion	15 mins	Successful OS policy case studies
10:00AM	17 - Open science policies support open science practices (KM5-6)	60 mins	Lecture/Interactive Activity - Discussion	30 mins	Open Science policies support Open Science practices
			Lecture	25 mins	Challenges of implementing and barriers to adopting Open Science
			Interactive Activity/Quiz	5 mins	Quiz
11:00AM	Break	10 mins			
11:10AM	17 - Open science policies support open science practices (KM5-6)	50 mins	Lecture	15 mins	Cultural Changes required for Open Science Adoption
			Interactive Activity/Discussion	15 min	Culture Assessment
			Lecture	15 mins	Open Science infrastructure
			Interactive Activity/Quiz	5 mins	Quiz
12:00PM	18 - Role of Policymakers in Supporting OS Practices (KM5-7-15)	75 mins	Lecture	20 mins	Profiles of Policy Makers supporting OS
			Lecture/Interactive Activity	25 mins	Essential Elements for OS policy development & implementation
			Lecture/Interactive Activity	25 mins	Responsible Research Assessment
			Interactive Activity/Quiz	5 mins	Quiz
1:15PM	Lunch Break	60 mins			
2:15PM	19 - Implementing OS policies - Action Planning	40 mins	Lecture	20 mins	Common Open Science Workflows

	and Roadmap Development		Interactive Activity/Discussion	20 mins	Overcoming Workflow Challenges
2:55PM	20 - Monitoring and Evaluation of Open Science Policies	45 mins	Lecture/Interactive Activity	30 mins	Monitoring progress and Impact - KPIs analysis
			Lecture	15 mins	Policy Adaptation
3:40PM	Closing Remarks and Course Summary	20 mins	Recap of Key Learnings	10 mins	
			Q&A Session	10 mins	
4:00PM	End of Course				

Community (pilot) trainings – initial estimations

As mentioned in section 3.1, within the MVS for each targeted professional profile, the organisational context is also identified, e.g for policymakers, the professional profiles can be found in the following categories:

- ministries (about research and beyond),
- governmental organisations,
- national agencies,
- national funding organisations,
- research performing organisations,
- data protection authorities.

The same approach is followed for the civil servants, with the MVS for this specific group being finalised at the moment of drafting this deliverable, the relevant categories include:

- governmental organisations,
- public administration,
- professionals in public bodies.

Having in mind the answers to the landscaping questionnaire for the targeted communities, we established an initial plan of the target groups that each country plans to focus on, during the national pilot trainings:

Table 10: Initial Plan for the community trainings

No.	Country	Groups of Target Profiles	Expected size	Estimated
-----	---------	---------------------------	---------------	-----------

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

		(policymakers and civil servants)	of audience (persons)	Date (month)
1	Italy	Funding Org./Ministries/Top level Research Performing Org.	10-15	M30-M32
2	Greece	Governmental Org./ Ministries/ Top level Research Performing Org.	15-30	M31-M33
3	Norway	Ministries/Top level Research Performing Org.	15-30	M29-M31
4	Spain	Governmental Org./ Funding Org./ Top level Research Performing Org.	10-20	M30-M32
5	Denmark	Governmental Org./ Funding Org./ Top level Research Performing Org./ Ministries	15-20	M30-M31
6	France	Top level Research Performing Org.	10-15	M31-M33
7	Finland	Top level Research Performing Org./ Funding Org./	20-30	M29-M31
8	UK	Governmental Org./ Top level Research Performing Org.	10-15	M30-M32
9	Sweden	Top level Research Performing Org.	20-30	M30-M32
10	Netherlands	Funding Org./ Top level Research Performing Org.	10-15	M30-M32
11	Belgium	Top level Research Performing Org.	10-15	M29-M31
12	Poland	Funding Org.	10-15	M30-M32
13	Germany	Top level Research Performing Org.	10-15	M31-M33
14	Estonia	Governmental Org./ Funding Org.	15-30	M29-M31
15	Austria	Top level Research Performing Org./ OS Professionals	10-20	M31-M33

In Table 3, each country identified initially the organisational context of the communities they could probably target, the size of the audience they have estimated, as well as the month of the project that they could organise the pilot training. More details on these trainings and the specific target communities will be identified during the training strategy meetings that are performed within WP3.

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

Based on these estimations, in Figure 7, an indicative timeline of the pilot training events that will take place during the Community training period is provided.

Figure 7: Indicative timeline of the planned pilot training events

In the meantime, during the material preparation phase, a lot of training events, related to this WP, will also take place, where partners of the consortium are involved. These events are out of the scope of the training activities of the WP and this deliverable, but they are mentioned as they will provide important insights and experience for the training development in Skills4EOSC.

All the planned training events of the project will be included in a calendar within the Skills4EOSC learning platform. This calendar will be updated regularly based on possible changes and modifications in the initial plans. As Skills4EOSC plans to conduct a large amount of training events during its lifetime, this schedule will support the consortium partners of the different WPs to organise their training events and avoid overlaps. Moreover, this calendar will serve trainees to be informed about future trainings that will be happening within the project. For the participation in the training events, trainer accreditation mechanisms will also be considered, based on the approach that will be designed in T2.5.

Finally, WP8 will support all the training development WPs in the dissemination of all the training events and the stakeholders engagement,

D3.1 - Policymakers and civil servants training plan

with relevant material, announcements, campaigns and communication approaches.

7 Conclusions

This deliverable reports the initial training activity plan related to T3.1 “Open Science training for policymakers and civil servants”. The aim is to analyse the foreseen activities in this task, as well as the necessary dependences with other tasks and WPs in the project, in order to provide a successful training on Open Science for evidence-based policy and public administration for policymakers and civil servants.

Moreover, it describes all the methodologies and tools that have been identified and will be followed in the different stages of the training procedures. From the Minimum Viable Skillsets, the FAIR-by-design methodology, the Training Material Preparation procedure and the Quality Assurance and certification framework, it is notable that there is a clear ambition in the project to provide high quality and tailored training material for each specific profile examined. Significant attention is also given to the identification of the proper trainers and communities that need to be targeted, in order to achieve valuable and efficient trainings.

Finally, the learning platform that is developed for the project will support the entire training process, not only by hosting all the necessary resources for the training material, but also by providing tools for the training delivery and evaluation. The calendar that will be integrated in the platform will be regularly updated with all the training events that will be performed in the project.

Since this is an initial plan, it is foreseen that some activities will probably change as we progress with the activities of the project. The updated plan and final results of the activities in T3.1 will be provided in D3.2 “Evidence-based policy and Public Administration training final report”.